

Virtual Acoustics: A software for simulating and auralizing acoustic environments

Lukas Aspöck
Institute for Hearing Technology and Acoustics
RWTH Aachen University
las@akustik.rwth-aachen.de

Satellite Workshop:
Unlocking the Potential of Open Research Software in Acoustics
29.08. & 30.08.2024

This work is licensed under [CC BY-SA 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/)

Virtual Acoustics (VA) – Today's overview

- 1 What is VA ? Why do we need it?
- 2 How did it start ?
- 3 Current development and discussion
- 4 More research software at IHTA

Virtual Acoustics: A research area (and a software)

*“The term **virtual acoustics** is often applied when a **sound signal is processed to contain features of a simulated acoustical space and sound is spatially reproduced** either with binaural or with multichannel techniques.”*

(Lokki & Savioja)

- Related key words: Acoustic simulation, Acoustic Virtual Reality, **Auralization**, Spatial Audio, Virtual Acoustic Environments

Lokki, T., Savioja, L. (2008). Virtual Acoustics. In: Havelock, D., Kuwano, S., Vorländer, M. (eds), Handbook of Signal Processing in Acoustics. Springer, New York, NY. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-30441-0_39

Auralization for scientific experiments

Goal: Realistic but reproducible conditions (in the lab)

Means: (Real-time) rendering of complex scenes

Virtual Acoustics: How does it work?

<https://git.rwth-aachen.de/ita/VA>

Main purpose: Application in scientific experiments

Schiller et al., 2023: Does a talker's voice quality affect university students' listening effort in a virtual seminar room? Forum Acusticum 2023, Turino, Italy

- VR classroom scenario experiment
 - Spatial reproduction of multiple sound sources (target speaker + background sound sources)
 - Real-time room simulation
 - Binaural reproduction
 - Speaking into virtual room

How it started...

Before 2000: Concepts and implementations for binaural reproduction and room simulation

Software development at IHTA

- **Around 2000-2010:**
 - First development of system- or project-specific C++ libraries
(e.g., binaural reproduction, room simulation, convolution [1-3])
 - No open-source repositories, only concept documentation in research papers
 - Version control system: CVS, later SVN (Apache Subversion)

- [1] Lentz, T. (2006). Dynamic crosstalk cancellation for binaural synthesis in virtual reality environments. *Journal of the Audio Engineering Society*, 54(4), 283-294.
- [2] Schröder, D., Wefers, F., Pelzer, S., Rausch, D., Vorländer, M., & Kahlen, T. (2010). Virtual reality system at RWTH Aachen University. In *Proceedings of the international symposium on room acoustics (ISRA), Melbourne, Australia*.
- [3] Wefers, F., & Berg, J. (2010). High-performance real-time FIR-filtering using fast convolution on graphics hardware. In *Proc. of the 13th Conference on Digital Audio Effects*.

Open-source software environments at IHTA

- **Around 2010-2015:**
 - New VR system in 2012 aixCAVE
 - More modular software architecture in project „Virtual Acoustics“ (Frank Wefers)
 - 2015: First stable versions of VA, decision to go open source ([Apache 2.0](#)) ; SVN → git
 - 2016: Public git repository, build automation using CMake (Jonas Stienen)
 - 2017: Project website www.virtualacoustics.org
 - **Regular releases of binary packages for Windows** (GPL / LGPL license)

How it is going ?

Recent years of the Virtual Acoustics software
Assessment and discussion of the recent developments

Virtual Acoustics: The last few years

Handover of software to next PhD generation

(Frank Wefers → Jonas Stienen → Philipp Schäfer → Pascal Palenda → ???)

Regular meetings both for developers and users (internal)

Revision of software architecture (rendering & reproduction modules, API changes)

Ongoing regular releases

More and more unit-testing, continuous integration

Virtual Acoustics: The last few years

- Regular application of the software inside and outside of the Institute in research experiments
- New rendering modules (including elaborated propagation models), e.g.,

AirTrafficNoise

UrbanNoise

Virtual Acoustics: Dissemination / Outreach

Improved documentation, changelog and archive of binaries on website

Regular presentation at conferences

Integration in teaching
(e.g., Acoustic Virtual Reality)

MATLAB examples for rendering configurations
(...hopefully more also soon for Python interface)

<https://git.rwth-aachen.de/ita/VAMatlab>

📁 aircraft_flyover

📁 car_passby

📁 general

📁 room_acoustics

📄 VA_example_offline_simulation.m

📄 VA_example_simple.m

Schäfer, P., Palenda P., Aspöck, L. and Vorländer, M. (2024). Plug-and-play tutorials for the auralization of complex scenarios using an open-source simulation framework. Proceedings of DAGA 2024, Hannover, Germany.

Virtual Acoustics: Evaluation - what's going well? Is it worth it?

Further research software at IHTA

RAVEN: Research software for GA-based room simulation and auralization

Efficient C++ implementation

Freely available for academia

Simple batch mode

MATLAB interface

VA rendering module

Real-time SketchUp interface

RAVEN

ITA-Toolbox: Open-source toolbox for audio data handling, measurements and simulations

- First open-source project at I(H)TA: started in 2008, open source since 2011
- Larger user group & wider application areas
- Much more contribution & commits

Berzborn, M., Bomhardt, R., Klein, J., Richter, J. G., & Vorländer, M. (2017). The ITA-Toolbox: An open source MATLAB toolbox for acoustic measurements and signal processing. In Proceedings of the 43th Annual German Congress on Acoustics, Kiel, Germany.

Pyfar: Open-source python packages for acoustics research

- Comprehensive framework: Audio data processing, plotting, acoustic measurements
- Various extensions, e.g., Sofar, Spharpy, Pyrato
- Ongoing work

pyfar

www.pyfar.org

- Virtual Acoustics: Powerful tool for academic research based on auralizations
- Overhead work of publishing, documenting and maintenance needs to be acknowledged
- Essential for reproducible, transparent research
- Challenges:
 - Keep it going ...
 - Technical complexity of the software and its application in research, esp. in combination with further hard- and software environment (e.g., in VR experiments)

www.virtualacoustics.org

Thank you for your attention

...and special thanks to the former and current main developers of Virtual Acoustics:

Frank Wefers, Jonas Stienen, Michael Kohnen, Philipp Schäfer and Pascal Palenda

Lukas Aspöck, Janina Fels, Michael Vorländer
Institute for Hearing Technology and Acoustics
las@akustik.rwth-aachen.de

